

PRINCIPLES OF CREATING THE "ANNOTATED DICTIONARY OF PARONYMS" FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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One of the main factors in the formation of independent thinking skills in students in the process of mother tongue education in secondary general education schools is to encourage students to use educational dictionaries both in the course of the lesson and in the process of independent education outside of the lesson. is to teach. After all, despite the fact that we need at least more than thirty educational dictionaries for the student to use in the process of learning a single mother tongue, we have only a few types of educational dictionaries. Unfortunately, they are not used enough in secondary schools. If we take into account that in the developed countries of the world, including English, German, French, etc., there are more than 20-30 types of educational dictionaries for students to use in their native language classes, we have a serious education in educational vocabulary. we feel the need for attention.

ABSTRACT

In this article considered the principles of drawing up the explanatory dictionary of paronymic words for school students

So, if one of the important tasks facing Uzbek linguistics is to compile and popularize educational dictionaries, teachers-mentors are responsible for pupils, students, educational and cultural workers from the first day of their activities related to social life. from the beginning, the task is to form a culture of wide and public use of dictionaries. /10,12/ Also, teachers have the responsibility to strive to form the spirit of need for knowledge in students, that is, to form the spirit of need to use dictionaries. Another important aspect should be noted here. A number of educational dictionaries were created by specialists who deeply understood the main goal of mother tongue education in secondary general education schools - to deliver a creative thinker to the society. O.Shukurov and B.Boymatova's "Learning dictionary of meaningful words of the Uzbek language", Yo.Khamrayeva's "Learning dictionary of words of the Uzbek

language", U. Torayeva and D.Shodmonova's "Learning dictionary of words with opposite meanings of the Uzbek language", B.Mengliyev and B.Bahriddinova's "Learning dictionary of word structure of the Uzbek language", H. Suvonova and G. Turdiyeva's "Educational dictionary of Uzbek language", T. Nafasov and V. Nafasova's "Educational toponymic dictionary of the Uzbek language", "Uzbek Dictionary of phonetic words of the Uzbek language", H.Norhojayeva's "Dictionary of obsolete words of the Uzbek language", B. Mengliyev, B. Bahriddinova, O'. Kholyirov, M. Zaripova and M. Khushvaktov's "Textbook of Uzbek language" is one of them. The dictionaries were warmly received by the public. About this in the newspaper "Marifat" "Alpomish in the cradle", "Alpomish in the cradle - a bouquet of dictionaries", in the magazine "Language and literature education" "New educational dictionaries", "Creating educational dictionaries" - urgent task" articles were published. Currently, it is expected that these dictionaries will be improved and publicly published on the scale of the republic, as well as delivered to the hands of schoolchildren. However, the work of creating and popularizing necessary dictionaries for schoolchildren cannot be left alone.

Similarly, the issue of creating and popularizing the "Explanatory Dictionary of Paronyms" for schoolchildren stems from the above-mentioned need to "form independent thinking skills in students."

It should be noted that in the speech of schoolchildren, such units as whiteness and whiteness, existence and existence, burch and burj, alpoz and alfoz or darz and dars, amr and amir, ahl and ahil, bob and bop, tib and tip, tub and tub are sometimes not

distinguished. we know Providing students with an explanatory dictionary of such paronymic pairs in a new way increases the child's language sensitivity and allows to get complete information about a specific word. /2, 120/

Studying paronyms on the basis of a systematic analysis helps to reveal that the vocabulary of the language is a whole system consisting of semantic fields and helps to develop the student's thinking. Based on this, it is necessary to work based on the following principles when compiling an explanatory dictionary of paronyms intended for schoolchildren: /10,141-142/.

- the principle of harmony of theory and practice. It is necessary that the materials given in the explanatory dictionary of paronyms correspond to the achievements in Uzbek linguistics in all respects, and in particular, the theory of paronymy should be seen in practice.

- the principle of alphabetical representation. Concepts in the dictionary should be given in alphabetical order, not within the framework of meaningful fields. This method is useful in teaching students to use ready-made material, as well as to conduct independent research, to think, to make comments and conclusions. In this way, today's person can develop the skills of using a new type of dictionary, as well as Internet materials.

- scientific principle. In the next 15-20 years, the direction of systematization, which is widely developing in Uzbek linguistics, should be reflected in the explanatory dictionary of paronyms to be created.

- the principle of education. An explanatory dictionary of paronyms is compiled for the purpose of students' learning, taking into account the current curriculum of the

native language and the requirements of DTS, as well as taking into account the age characteristics of the learners.

- the principle of commenting without commenting. The lexemes given in the paronymic explanatory dictionary should be simple and understandable. For example, the user of the dictionary should easily understand that the lexeme *adl* has the meanings of "justice", "correctness", "justice" /11,45/. As a result of its semantic combination with lexemes such as *force*, *power*, *leader*, *supporter*, it creates a separate positive field of understanding (power of justice, power of justice, leaders of justice, supporters of justice), and on the other hand, with the theme of "injustice" *ignorance*, *ignorance*, *injustice*, *indolence* should understand that it forms a semantic line with opposite meaning with the lexemes in its form, and therefore should be able to make an explanation without an explanation.

- the generality-specificity principle. It is important to work based on the dialectic of generality and particularity when creating a dictionary. In this way, the relationships between lexemes, such as semantic similarity, nesting, type-genus, whole-piece, gradation, etc., are determined, which helps to illuminate the diversity of the expressed essence.

-consistency principle. In the explanatory dictionary of paronyms, it is necessary that the lexemes presented in the fields of concepts do not mix with each other, but must be united under a clear plan.

Theoretical and practical issues of creating an explanatory dictionary of paronyms in the Uzbek language can be solved only if the above requirements are met. /3, 8-21/
When compiling an explanatory dictionary of paronyms using the concept field, it is

necessary to take into account the paradigmatic, syntagmatic and hierarchical characteristics of paronymic pairs. Because paronyms also have various characteristics in this regard. As an example, let's turn to the polynomial paronymic pair *adil* and *adl*. This paronymic pair has a phonetic similarity. Although these words, which mean multiple meanings such as *straight*, *not bent*, *not bent*, *straight*, *straight*, are close to each other in terms of meaning, they have syntagmatic characteristics. according to contradict each other. For example, it is possible to say *adil kamat*, *adil bas*, *adil terak*, *adil navda*, but it cannot be replaced by the combinations of *adil kocha*, *adil yol*, *adil got*, *adil gormak*, *street*, *road*, *go*, and *go*. . In a paronymic dictionary, such issues will undoubtedly find their solution. Also, in such a dictionary, relationships such as paronymic, hyper-hyponymic, graduonymic are expressed as much as possible (if such features exist). In this way, the explanatory dictionary of paronyms reflects the dialectical relationship of world - consciousness - language /2, 15/.

Here it should be noted that there are differences in defining the boundaries of paronyms in Uzbek linguistics. This puts a lot of "shadow" on the work of creating a dictionary. For example, Shoabdurahmanov Sh. etc. in the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language" under the topic "Paronyms" the following is noted: "Words with different phonetic structure, similar in pronunciation and remaining close are called paronyms. The phenomenon of such a relationship between words is called paronymy. Fact - pact, *afzal* - *abzal*, *amr* - *amir*, etc. So, paronymy occurs as a result of not pronouncing in the literary norm, not

knowing the literary pronunciation norm, as well as the phonetic structure of the word correctly.

From what was said about homonyms, homophones, homographs and paronyms, it became clear that in them two or more words form a mutual unity according to their formal relationship and pronunciation. The meaning of the words is not important in this regard. /8, 51/

In the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language" by U. Tursunov and others under the topic "Lexical paronymy" the following is noted: "Lexical paronymy. In order for two lexemes to be mutually paronymous (from Greek raga - "next to", opuma - "name") they must: 1) be artificial lexemes, 2) be derived from the same lexeme, 3) belong to the same category 4) the content plan of the constituent morphemes should be common, 5) the constituent morphemes should be similar in terms of the expression plan. The following international lexemes borrowed from the Russian language correspond to the requirements listed above, so they are considered paronyms: Abonent ("owner of a subscription") - subscription ("a document that gives the right to use something for a certain period of time"); where: a) basis of creation - subscription; b) makers- -yent, -yement...

Lexical paronyms are also defined based on simpler requirements: two lexemes that differ by only one phoneme in the system of phonemes are considered mutual paronyms. If such a requirement is sufficient, alpoz ("condition", "good") - alfoz (plural lexeme of the word), abzal (original afzor: "tool", "saddle") - afzal ("good", "excess"), khalar ("free")-kholos ("only"), zhizmaq ("to draw a line")- draw ("draw a line"), hush ("good", "pleasant" -

hush (Pairs such as "a person's ability to perceive, perceive, understand"), rukh I (the name of one of the chess pieces - "tora") - rukh ("mood reflecting the feelings of a person") can be called paronyms. /7, 49/

Here are some mutually exclusive examples:

- In the book "Lexicology of the Uzbek language", let's pay attention to the relationship between the words amr and amir. The word amr has the lexical meaning of command, and amir has the lexical meaning of giving orders. These words belong to the Arabic language and are made in a way specific to this language. In it, a new word is created by changing the vowels or increasing the vowels without changing the consonants of the word. Similar words such as waqf, coffee, and nature are derived from the words waqif, cafe, and nature. There is no paronymic relationship between such root words and words derived from them. /9, 255/.

- Shoabdurakhmanov and others. In the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language": Words with different phonetic structure, similar in pronunciation, and remaining close are called paronyms. The phenomenon of such a relationship between words is called paronymy. Fact - pact, afzal - abzal, amr - amir, etc. /8, 51/

- In the book "Lexicology of the Uzbek language" such lines as bod and bot, yod and yot, mard and mart, kiyd and kayt, sob and sop, tub and tup, company and campaign, share and share are not paronyms, but homophones. /9, 55/

- Rahmatullayev Sh. In the book "Current Literary Uzbek Language": ...bob-bop, tib-tip, yot-yod, sukkhor-uskhor, fufuz-nufus,... company - campaign... are homophones. /6, 42-44/

-Pinkhasov Ya.D. "Current literary Uzbek language. In the book "Lexicology and Phraseology", the words tug-tuk, tuz-tus, tub-tup, sudkhor-sukkhор, tambur-tanbur, sher-sher are considered homophones in the Uzbek language.

- Shoabdurakhmanov and others. In the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language": The difference between homophones is in one phoneme in their composition. But these phonemes are also very close to each other in terms of phonetic properties. For this reason, the pronunciation of these words is the same: tub-tup, yod-yot, bob-bop, mard-mart, tanbur-tambur, sudkhor-sukkhор, bod-bot, sud - sut and b.

- Olimov M. in the book "Ilmul-luguoт or lexicology": Words that are pronounced and written differently, but whose form is extremely close to each other, are called paronymous words. For example: asr-asir, tanbur-tambur, nufuz-nufus,... /5, 72/

- In the 5th grade "Mother Tongue" textbook: Words whose pronunciation and spelling are very close to each other, but have different meanings, are called paronyms. remember - read, chapter - chapter, get rid of - trick - trick, scold - body, aro-oro. /2, 119-120/

- In the book "Lexicology of the Uzbek language": Paronyms are characterized by similarity in pronunciation.

- Shoabdurakhmanov and others. In the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language": ... similar in pronunciation... words are called paronyms... The meaning of the words is not important in this.

- Olimov M. in the book "Ilmul-luguoт or lexicology": It is said and written differently..... words are called paronymous words.

- Tursunov U. and others. In the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language": Due to

the extreme similarity in pronunciation, there are difficulties in using such lexemes, inappropriate usage, etc.

As can be seen from the above simple comparisons, there are a number of confusions and differences in the definition of paronyms, in defining their boundaries, and in the examples given in textbooks and training manuals.

In our opinion, the essence of paronymy is based on the two-way phonetic and semantic relations of mutually harmonious words. /7, 55/ It is theoretically necessary to rely on this principle when compiling a dictionary of paronyms.

The analysis shows that the most paronymous words are related to the concepts of a person and his characteristics, and when including them in the semantic field, synonyms, antonyms, graduonyms, etc. of each paronymic pair should not be overlooked. Only then will a dictionary be created that can meet the needs and requirements of today's schoolchildren. For example, just

Adil - the origin of the word: Arabic word - "equal", "equal"; according to the meaning of atash: a word with multiple meanings. 1. Synonyms: straight, not bent, not bent, upright; opposite meaning: bent, crooked; nestmates: straight, unbent, unbent, straight, upright, basulat; syntactic connection: adil komat, adil head, adil terak, adil navda, etc.; 2. Synonyms: unturned, unturned, straight, straight; opposite meaning: -; nestmates: untwisted, unturned, flat, straight, smooth, straight; syntactic connection: fair street, fair road, fair going, fair going, etc.;

Adl - the origin of the word: Arabic word - "justice", "correctness"; according to the meaning of atash: a word with one

meaning; synonyms: justice, correctness, justice; opposite meanings: ignorance, ignorance, injustice, injustice, indolence; nestmates: justice, correctness, fairness, honesty, impartiality; syntactic connection: the power of justice, the power of justice, leaders of justice, supporters of justice better - better

Abzal - the origin of the word: Persian word - "tool", "working tool"; according to the meaning of atash: a word with one meaning; synonyms: tool, working tool; opposite meaning: -; nestmates: belt, yugan, harness, jazliq, saddle, kyishkhan, uzangi, yoke; syntactic connection: set of parts, parts of parts, value of parts, etc.;

Afzal - the origin of the word: the Arabic word - "the most virtuous", "the most virtuous"; according to the meaning of atash: a word with multiple meanings; 1. Synonyms: good, excellent, more; opposite meanings: bad, low, not possible, not possible, bad; nestmates: durust, binoyi, binoyi, good, excellent, excellent, no less, more, more, more, etc.; syntactic connection: preferred mood, preferred day, preferred friend, preferred habit, preferred to see, preferred to know, preferred to count, etc.; 2. Synonyms: More, More, More; opposite meanings: -; nestmates: all male names;

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